

Table 2. Mean grain yield, yield components, PFP, and ANUE for 1998.

Treatment	Tillers pot ⁻¹ (no.)	1,000-grain wt (g)	Grain yield (g m ⁻²)	Grains panicle ⁻¹ (no.)	PFP ^a (kg kg ⁻¹ N)	ANUE ^b (kg kg ⁻¹ N)
<i>Good water management</i>						
No N	5.2	21	111	60.0	—	—
POCU ^c	11.8	23	354	77.5	59.0	40.5
Urea	14.3	23	330	57.7	54.9	36.5
5% LSD ^d	2.1 ^e		44 ns	14.1 ^e	4.6 ns	12.8 ns
<i>Poor water management</i>						
No N	7.8	21	133	47.1	—	—
POCU ^c	13.3	21	343	71.6	57.2	35.0
Urea	12.8	21	261	57.1	43.4	21.2
5% LSD ^d	2.1 ns		44 ^e	14.1 ^e	4.6 ^e	12.8 ^e

^aPFP (partial factor productivity) = Yield/N_x. ^bANUE (agronomic nitrogen-use efficiency) = (Yield at N_x - yield at N₀)/applied N at N_x. ^cPOCU is a controlled-release fertilizer; in 1998, the combination of LP40 and LPS100 was 1:1. ^dLSD is a comparison between POCU and prilled urea. ^e = significant at P = 0.05. ns = not significant.

under the urea treatment (Table 2). The POCU treatment performed significantly better than prilled urea, either with leaching alone or with a combination of

leaching and surface runoff. This can be attributed to the slow-release pattern of N, which matches the need of the plant,

consequently giving POCU more grains per panicle.

In 1997, partial factor productivity (PFP)—but not agronomic nitrogen-use efficiency (ANUE)—of the POCU treatment under PWM was significantly higher than that of the urea treatment. However, in 1998, both PFP and ANUE of the POCU treatment were significantly higher than those of the urea treatment. This implies that the slow-release mechanism of polyolefin-coated urea enhances N-use efficiency of the plant. This better performance of POCU under PWM indicates a potential for increased rice yield if POCU is basally applied at 60 kg N ha⁻¹ to nutritionally poor soil with high N leaching loss.

Nitrogen source and application time before flooding affect rice yield in Spain

R. Carreres, J. Sendra, R. Ballesteros, Departamento del Arroz, Instituto Valenciano de Investigaciones Agrarias, Sueca 46410, Valencia, Spain; E. Fernández-Valiente, A. Quesada, D. Carrasco, M. Crespo, and F. Leganés, Departamento de Biología, Universidad Autónoma de Madrid, 28049 Madrid, Spain E-mail: r.carreres@master.ivia.es

Valencian rice growers usually apply excess N, which results in loss of soil quality because of its negative effects on the soil N₂-fixing cyanobacteria (Carreres et al 1996). In Valencia, constraints in the irrigation system have led to lack of control in water management, with difficulties in irrigating after incorporating N fertilizer. The low N efficiency reflects substantial N losses (Fernández Valiente et al 2000). Improving N efficiency and soil use by preserving and developing the ability of N₂-fixing organisms for biofertilization would reduce N fertilizer use and result in ecological, economic, and environmental benefits. N efficiency cannot be improved by split application in Valencia (Carreres et al 1998) but it can be enhanced by slow-release fertilizers (SRF) in Europe (Moletti et al 1989). The relationships between N₂ fixation, physical and chemical characteristics of water and sediments, and rates and

timing of inorganic N fertilizers were described in previous papers (Quesada et al 1997, Carreres et al 1998). Studies dealing with the effect of SRF on N₂ fixation are lacking. This work evaluates the use of different SRF and nitrification inhibitors (NI) in rice fields of Valencia, Spain.

Experiments were conducted during 1998-99 at the Rice Department in Valencia, Spain. Eight N sources (ammonium sulfate [AS], urea, polymer-coated urea [PCU, 32% and 40% N], sulfur-coated urea [MSCU], isobutylidene diurea [IBDU], N ammoniacal form [AF] + dicyandiamide [DCD, 11:1], and AF + dimethyl pyrazolo phosphate [DMPP, 11:1], including a control [no N] were applied at 120 kg N ha⁻¹ and at 2 or 15 d before flooding (DBF) during 1998. Four N sources (urea blended with PCU [40% N] at four ratios: 1:0, 3:1, 1:1, 1:3) were applied at four rates (70, 95, 120, and 145

kg N ha⁻¹) and at 15 DBF during 1999.

Treatment plots, each replicated four times, were laid out in a split-plot design (delay in flooding after N application as main plot and N source as subplot) during 1998 and in a randomized block design in 1999. N fertilizer was given as a single broadcast application. After flooding, seeds were broadcast at 180 kg ha⁻¹.

In June and July 1998, *in situ* acetylene-reducing activity (ARA) was measured only in plots where fertilizer was applied 2 DBF (see table). At crop maturity, grain and straw yields and N content in plants were determined (Carreres et al 1996). In 1998, traits were subjected to a split-plot analysis of variance (N source and timing) and in 1999 to a one-way (no N and 16 treatments: four N sources at four N rates) and a split-plot (N rates as main plot and N source as subplot) analysis of variance.

Effect of N source and delay in flooding after N application on N₂ fixation, grain yield, and N content, N uptake, and N efficiencies.^a

N source	ARA ^b	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)		Grain ^c N content (%)	N uptake ^c (kg ha ⁻¹)	AE		RE (%) ^c Δ plant N/ applied N
		Δ grain yield/applied N				15 ddf	2 ddf	
		15 ddf	2 ddf					
1998								
No N	24.0 a	6.13 d	6.59 d	1.00 c	85.9 c	—	—	—
AS	3.0 b	7.78 c	8.90 abc	1.14 a	137.2 ab	13.7 cd	19.2 abcd	42.7 ab
CU	7.7 b	8.19 abc	8.69 abc	1.11 ab	135.2 ab	17.1 abcd	17.4 abcd	41.0 ab
PCU (32% N)	13.3 a	8.26 abc	8.46 abc	1.12 a	132.4 b	17.7 abcd	15.6 bcd	38.7 b
MSCU	6.3 b	8.22 abc	8.77 abc	1.12 a	138.2 ab	17.4 abcd	18.2 abcd	43.5 ab
PCU (40% N)	21.3 a	9.37 a	9.15 ab	1.13 a	147.8 a	26.9 a	21.3 abcd	51.5 a
IBDU	21.7 a	8.95 abc	8.74 abc	1.08 b	134.6 ab	23.5 abc	17.9 abcd	40.5 ab
DCD	10.3 ab	8.86 abc	8.69 abc	1.12 a	142.6 ab	22.7 abcd	17.4 abcd	47.2 ab
DMPP	9.4 ab	9.04 ab	8.14 bc	1.11 ab	138.1 ab	24.4 ab	12.9 d	43.5 ab
SE N source (48 df)	6.84 ^d	0.347	0.012	4.25	2.94 ^e			3.68 ^e
1999								
No N	—	4.08 ^f	1.06 ^f	57.0 ^f	—	—	—	—
100% CU	—	7.46 b	1.10 a	105.2 b	30.7 b	—	—	43.5 b
75% CU + 25% PCU	—	7.18 b	1.08 a	108.2 b	29.0 b	—	—	47.2 b
50% CU + 50% PCU	—	7.48 b	1.10 a	110.6 b	32.6 b	—	—	50.8 b
25% CU + 75% PCU	—	8.03 a	1.11 a	120.1 a	38.6 a	—	—	61.2 a
SE N source (45 df)	—	0.183	0.012	3.34	1.90	—	—	3.24

^aIn 1998, split-plot design (four replications); in 1999, randomized complete block design (four replications), means of four N rates. In each year, means in a column followed by the same letter are not significantly different ($P = 0.05$) by Duncan's multiple range test (DMRT); AS = ammonium sulfate; CU = conventional urea; PCU = polymer-coated urea; MSCU = sulfur-coated urea; IBDU = isobutylidene diurea; DCD = N inhibitor; DMPP = N inhibitor; ARA = acetylene-reducing activity (mmol ethylene h⁻¹ m⁻²); AE = agronomic efficiency; RE = recovery efficiency; df = degrees of freedom; ddf = days delay in flooding. ^bMean of two sampling periods, analysis of variance conducted on data transformed to log (1 + x). The table gives backtransformed values. ^cIn 1998, means of two delays in flooding (interaction "delay × N source" was not significant). ^d24 df. ^e42 df. ^fControl treatment (no N) was significantly different (grain yield and N uptake) or not (grain N content) from all other treatments (four rates × four N sources; data not shown).

Duncan's multiple range test (DMRT) and orthogonal polynomial contrasts were used to test differences.

In June–July, N from SRF (PCU and IBDU) had been totally released and soil inorganic N level was lower in plots fertilized with SRF than with conventional fertilizers (CF), with or without NI. Therefore, N₂ fixation during months with maximum ARA values (Carreres et al 1996) was not affected by SRF (PCU and IBDU) application compared with when N fertilizer was absent (see table). This trend was similar to that reported by Carreres et al (1998) for split N application.

SRF, particularly PCU 40% N applied basally before flooding, was the best N source for grain yield and improved agronomic efficiency (AE) and recovery efficiency (RE) (see table). However, it was only significant when applied 15 DBF (significant interaction between N source and DBF) and compared with AS. These results agree with the findings of Moletti et al (1989) and the orthogonal contrasts confirm the results ($P < 0.05$). Accordingly, in 1999 and as shown by orthogonal polynomial contrasts, grain yield ($P < 0.01$),

N uptake, and N efficiency ($P < 0.05$) increased linearly as the coated-conventional urea ratio increased. This indicates that the slow N release effectively reduced substantial N losses resulting from the delay in flooding after N application using CF, alone or blended with NI. N losses can be attributed more to ammonia volatilization than to nitrification-denitrification processes, thus confirming the findings of Fernández Valiente et al (2000).

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